

Anonymized Community Comments

Comments in this appendix come from the modeling community in Heliophysics, Climate Science, and Earth Science among others. The people contributing these comments are not indicated for privacy reasons. Portions of original comments indicating the modeler's home institution or company have been edited out. All comments have been reviewed and approved by their contributors.

Acronyms

A list of acronyms used in the comments below.

- CCMC = Community Coordinated Modeling Center
- AO = Announcement opportunity, e.g. in ROSES
- ROSES = Research Opportunities in Space and Earth Science
- CSCCE = Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement

Modelers and Related Experts

Modeler 1

- Thinks requirement that large modeling code be open source is too much.
- But description should be available that is more detailed than the publication (e.g. on GitHub).
- Expects people to contact the developers if they want to work on details, like for science quality runs.
- Users need a thorough understanding of the physics and the code itself to understand how to set up the code to run. True for most of the major MHD codes. Code will crash, or worse, run but give unphysical results if the run is set up wrong.
- Could do basic checks on inputs and settings to give warnings through the GUI or notebook, but can't warn for the entire parameter space.
- Even the model developers have to run/rerun their own model to debug what is going on.
- Models looking for validation or wide use would benefit from a pared-down version of the model that can be run online through a GUI/notebook.
- **For other people to run the code and debug a given run, would take years of training.** Easier to handle installation errors than run debugging.
- Version at CCMC often a pared down version, but **people often run it and then cite the full version, which is not only inaccurate but can cast doubt on the full version!**
- Should be **financial support for missions/modelers to give updates to the community** on status, improvements, intro to data analysis with the datasets, new analysis capabilities. This would greatly help new scientists learn how to use the missions and models.

- Need a structure for funding such workshops for models and to upkeep/improve the code.
- Wary of competing modeling codes against each other like missions do because the main people that would have the appropriate background to review the proposal would either be on the proposal or a direct competitor. Prefer to keep competing the science, but not the modeling codes.
- Maybe instead of a new AO, include X amount of possible additional funds in current AOs to host workshops, make model improvements to better answer a science question, etc.

Modeler 2

CCMC has a reasonable approach to describing its models (e.g. <https://ccmc.gsfc.nasa.gov/models/SWMF~20140611/>) but leaves much to be desired in its descriptions and model search interface. Model pages do not have sample visualizations, links to a data search for that model, publications known to have used data from that model, tutorials on how to install and use that model, or example uses of the outputs. This example is better: <https://ccmc.gsfc.nasa.gov/models/OpenGGCM~4.0>. Yet there is no indication of versions or differences from the version at the model developers' institution. Makes the developers look bad when people publish using data from CCMC that doesn't match well, but point to the full model version (and inappropriately so). Need to be able to cite the version of the model used to produce the dataset to improve apparent model performance

Modeler 3

- need a way to plug and play via syntax, but doing this via ascii headers is outdated, need to update this (eg docstrings).
- Ideally, the community will work together on a given physics modeling unit (eg radiative transfer), can have multiple version of the same unit done with different approaches,
- preferably open so anyone can add to it or run it with their own parameters

Modeler 4

- for reproducibility, need to give output dataset, parameter values, and executable file used to run the model. (Executable file is separate from the source code.)
- need to be able to search model outputs to run mining exercises.
- Also many pared down models can't be run on the cloud on more than one CPU because they are written in unparallelized Fortran/C/C++ so can't take advantage of multiple processors.

Modeler 5

- AI as a way to sidestep some of the resolution constraints with approximation tools, emulators can be trained on outputs to decrease costs,
- AI can be used for inverse problem (limiting the parameter space to match an observation),

- AI can learn the behavior of small scale processes to inform the larger scale processes (eg effect of sound waves on things that may effect the solar wind) and to start connecting systems on different time/spatial scales,
- AI can help pull in the elements of chaotic behavior to larger scale processes that are missed with averaging

Modeler 6

- Where is the field going next? A desire to connect strongly with observations and to move beyond our theoretical climate sandbox.
- Problems: many unknowns, massive parameters spaces to explore degeneracies between climate states and observations, global climate models are prohibitively expensive.
- Solution: sparse gridded large parameter space studies, create large databases of models (and outputs), use to inform retrievals, interpretations of observations, target selections and future mission design.

Modeler 7

- Need robust validation and verification frameworks for models, e.g. <https://github.com/ServiceNow/geo-bench>
- A few (new) literacies our community needs suggested by the structure that another suggests: facilitation, digital/virtual group administration, community manager (e.g., [CSCCE's scientific community manager](#))

Modeler 8

Portion of a presentation from a group of modelers relevant to modeling infrastructure.

Searching for Tools: Can we find the tools?

Stages to calculate the aurora:

- Need outputs from the star (wind, CME output).
- Tool that describes interaction of wind/CME with magnetosphere MHD.
- See whether electron/particle precipitation fluxes interact to produce H3+, calculate emission power in IR.

Using knowledge from SME, expected tools are:

- AWSoM
- BATS-R-US
- H3ppy
- tools to read and plot model outputs in 3D, input results of one code into another codes

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Problems Encountered: EMAC model search

EMAC

- No description or listing of variables output by the modeling code. Can't search by variables.
- No star rating for ease of use, ability to install on different OS (e.g. Mac vs Windows), relevance
- No listing of cross-disciplinary tools on EMAC.
(Points to a lack of a search interface across sciences for software tools. Could be solved by adding schema.org metadata to descriptive landing pages for software so that internet search engines can find it).
- Many listings don't have more information beyond a single paragraph.
- Tools chosen with previous knowledge not listed! (BATS-R-US, AWSoM, h3ppy)
- Search results not alphabetized.

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Problems Encountered: CCMC Model Search

- No way to compare between the many model results on CCMC's website. Must compare 10-20 models to choose, too large of a barrier for many.
- Can only search by category and name, not by descriptions, variable outputs, or similar items.
- Not a complete listing of all models in Heliophysics/Geophysics.
- No distinguishing of version numbers compared to what is installed at the developer's institutions.
- No link to community tools to read, interpolate and plot outputs.
- Data given to user not in the original format needed to use community tools.
- No DOIs to properly cite the correct version of the model used.
- No way to run models with parameters relevant for exoplanetary research.

Moving Forward: Infrastructure Needs

- a more general search for software across science areas for interdisciplinary research.
- more descriptive metadata for models' landing pages (e.g. variable inputs and outputs, version numbers, DOIs, related community software).
- better search to incorporate all of these aspects in the results.
- data reading, plotting, and interpolation tools for model outputs to be available in community software.
- direct access to run model code ourselves, possibly using the cloud.
- software to make it easier to drive one model with the output of another.
- 1-5 star ratings based on tool usability, tool quality, accuracy of description.

Modeler 9

A small group of modelers and forecasters.

- Standards needed in model software face decades of effort on legacy code. Any new standard desired by the community should be forward-looking
- Needs to improve crowd-sourcing of improvements to modeling code
- Usability of models (e.g. installing pared down versions of the code on the cloud and allowing anyone to run it for themselves)
- Serving the file reader/interpolator with the data better than pushing for a set of standard file formats.
- setting a data file format standard is useless. Better to serve the reader and plotting script with the dataset and let the community do whatever they want with the file format. If we have an API to serve data from with the associated reader/plotting scripts, and that can convert into common data formats (e.g. CSV, JSON, netCDF, FITS, etc), then the original file format becomes irrelevant.
- How to get the data produced by models to be searchable?

Modeler 10

- Complex process to get model validation done. Need a structure to enable community efforts to validate models beyond anecdotal case studies, particularly for operational agencies to *believe* the effort.

Forecasting Expert

- The software dependencies of any model and any graphical interface or web application that accompanies it should be compatible with technologies supported by forecasting infrastructure. Open science helps address some of these issues as the technical details are clear right from the start. The use of modern infrastructure and technologies should hopefully speed the transition of research to a proving ground for evaluation. But it is probably worth noting that some modern solutions may not yet be implemented at the ops centers
- There has to be a clear **turn key way of running and rerunning** (and rerunning and rerunning) the model for those events/observations, particularly if there's a model upgrade to get updated metrics and confirm things are still looking good. Unit tests are important too, to make sure the developers' results can be replicated in an environment that specifically mimics the ops environment.

Cloud / Open Science Expert

- Effort moving forward to allow users to run models and other complex code on government HPCs such as Cheyenne from the cloud.
- Curated collection of tools built to work together needs to be the motivation and purpose for user workshops.
- Need customizability for open source tools for international use.
- Increasing sophistication of tools means that validation of that tool becomes more important (e.g. SunPy vs modeling code).
- How to encourage contribution to a software rather than forking and repeating work? A contact person for the software available for questions about whether a change is being worked on?
- 'Open' is not a command; 'open' is an opportunity. Need systems that allow sharing but allow the data/software/etc provider to control the scope.

Jack Eddy 2023 Attendees

Attendees of the 4th Jack Eddy Symposium contributed their input into what they thought was easy, critical, and difficult in making their model-related codes more usable by others and in using model-related codes developed by others. Screenshots of those inputs are below and are available at <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVNUbZGvk=/>. The text of some of the comments are too small to display in a single image, so the portions of the Miro boards are split into two images each. Similar input for software supporting publications can be found on the left side of the Miro board, but is not included below since it is not relevant to this work.

Figure 1: Input from attendees of the 4th Jack Eddy Symposium on what is easy, critical or difficult when attempting to use someone else's model-related code. The comments on the right side are repeated in the next image zoomed in due to the small text size.

Figure 2: Input from attendees of the 4th Jack Eddy Symposium on what is easy, critical or difficult when attempting to use someone else's model-related code. The comments in this figure are the same as those on the right side of Figure 1 but zoomed in due to the small text size.

Figure 3: Input from attendees of the 4th Jack Eddy Symposium on what is easy, critical or difficult when making their own model-related code usable by others. The comments on the right bottom corner are repeated in the next image zoomed in due to the small text size.

Figure 4: Input from attendees of the 4th Jack Eddy Symposium on what is easy, critical or difficult when making their own model-related code usable by others. The comments in this figure are the same as those on the right bottom corner of Figure 3 but zoomed in due to the small text size.